

**PRACTICAL APPLICATION OF PYTHON IN SOLVING
MATHEMATICAL PROBLEMS**

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Annotation. The article studied methods for writing programs that solve mathematical scientific problems in the Python programming language.

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INTRODUCTION

The article studied how to write programs that solve scientific problems in the Python programming language has a clear and understandable syntax, and therefore it is easy to learn and well suited for programming. This will allow not to be distracted from the problem being solved by the features of the language and their explanation, and will naturally consistently introduce new tools. The language is close to MATLAB and is good for programming mathematical calculations. In addition, Python can work with languages such as Fortran, C and C ++, which are already widely used in scientific calculations. Among other things, most products and modules written in Python are distributed free of charge[1].

Programming helps develop computational thinking. Computational thinking, in turn, develops problem-solving skills, creative thinking, learning skills, and teamwork skills. Learning how to program is not necessary to become a programmer in the future. The main task of programming is to "prepare" for computational thinking, which helps to confidently cope with complex problems that do not have a unique solution. If you learn how to disassemble a large problem into smaller stages, find similarities in different elements, identify and eliminate the insignificant, combine fragments into a

single algorithm to obtain a result, then this will help solve problems in any discipline [2].

Python is a popular programming language used both for developing standalone programs and for scripting applications in a wide variety of applications. It is an easy to use and free programming language. Programmers from a wide variety of disciplines find that Python's emphasis on development efficiency and high-quality software gives it a strategic advantage on projects both small and large. Python is open source software, i.e. no license is required to use it. Moreover, Python is included by default in Linux distributions, Macintosh computers and some other software and hardware products, which makes it difficult to estimate the number of users of this programming language. In general, the number of Python users is much larger and has a very active developer community around it[3].

In the article, the subject of research is the possibility of solving mathematical problems in the Python programming language. Using the Python programming language, you can solve various mathematical problems. To achieve this goal, it will be necessary to solve the following tasks:

- Study the history of the creation of this programming language;
- Analyze the advantages and disadvantages of the Python programming language;
- Study the algorithm for solving quadrant equations;
- Create code to solve quadratic equations.

Thus, the hypothesis of my research is that with the help of the Python programming language it is possible to solve various mathematical problems, in particular quadratic equations[4].

RESULTS and DISCUSSIONS

The Dutchman Guido Van Rossum is the author of Python (from the word Monthy Python). He began developing this language in the late 1980s while working at the Dutch CWI Institute. In February 1990, Guido posted the source code to the alt.sources newsgroup. In 2000, the second part of Python was released. Many important things

have been added, including a garbage collector and Unicode support. In 2008, on December 3, the third release was released, so far the last one. Python is a simple language[4].

Benefits of the Python programming language:

1) Simplicity. This programming language is often recommended as the first "core" language because it is very easy to learn and use. In the process of writing a program, the use of curly braces is not required, as in other languages, which allows you not to be distracted by switching between keys and pay more attention to the development of the program.

2) Extensiveness of application. Python is used almost everywhere: for creating websites, games, software development, 3D modeling, and even photo editing. To do this, there are various language tools and programs. Many large companies (Google, Instagram, Facebook) use Python.

3) Licensed and free. The main advantage of this language is the availability of a license, accessibility and free. This allows you to use Python without restrictions, even in schools. You can also learn how to speak this language for free through various courses and video tutorials.

4) Support. Python is supported by developers and the programming community (ordinary users), so if you run into any problem, you can always find out how to solve it directly by contacting the developers.

5) Extensive libraries. Python has standard libraries where you can work with electronic resources, databases, Internet protocols, and other tools needed for specific purposes.

6) Suitable for most types of modern operating systems. Scripts written in Python are suitable for iOS, Android, Windows and other OS types. This allows you to use the programming language in a variety of areas, which greatly expands its capabilities.

7) Perspective. This is one of the main factors for learning Python - the language will be in demand for a few more years due to its merits.

Disadvantages of the Python programming language:

1) Unusual syntax. If you are learning Python as not the first programming language, then it will be difficult to get used to it due to the lack of brackets and some signs. But if the language is studied as a basic one, then this problem is solved.

2) Low program execution speed. Programs written in Python are slower than similar programs written in other languages. But this problem can be solved with the help of special virtual machines.

3) Incorrect copying of the code. If you copy the program code from another resource, it will be inserted into the text without indents and will not work. You should take the time to add spaces.

4) Converting the program to exe. Programs written in Python have a py extension and must be converted to exe for use on Windows. After that, the amount of memory occupied by the program increases several times. The problem of increasing memory can be solved by removing unnecessary libraries, but after this action, the program may work worse.

5) Inability to write drivers. Some programmers point out that Python is not designed for writing software drivers because it doesn't have the tools to do so.

6) Incompatibility of different language versions. Python 2.x and Python 3.x will coexist for the time being and in the next few releases, with the second version being used for compatibility. However, the third version is not compatible with the second, and there will be an error when writing Python 2.x codes on Python 3.x.

Now let's get acquainted with the practical application of Python in solving mathematical problems. For this practical application of this programming language, we will check on the example of solving quadratic equations [5].

A quadratic equation is an equation of the form

$$ax^2+bx+c=0,$$

where a, b, c are some numbers (coefficients), $a \neq 0$.

All the coefficients of a quadratic equation are interconnected by a formula called the discriminant.

The program code looks like this:

```

import math
print("Input coefficients")
print("ax^2 + bx + c = 0:")
a = float(input("a = "))
b = float(input("b = "))
c = float(input("c = "))
discr = b**2 - 4*a*c
print("Discriminant D = %.2f" % discr)
if discr > 0:
    x1 = (-b + math.sqrt(discr)) / (2 * a)
    x2 = (-b - math.sqrt(discr)) / (2 * a)
    print("x1 = %.2f \nx2 = %.2f" % (x1, x2))
elif discr == 0:
    x = -b / (2 * a)
    print("x = %.2f" % x)
else:
    print("No solve")

```

The above code was used to solve a quadratic equation in Python 3. Let's look at some of the things that were used in this simple program[6]:

- print - This function prints information to the screen.
- input - Displays information and prompts the user for input.
- b**2 is exponentiation, in this case b is squared.
- str - this function converts the data to a string.
- if-elif-else are condition statements in Python. By the value of the discriminant, we determine the number of roots of the quadratic equation.
- discriminant ** 0.5 - this method extracts the square root. There are several ways to extract roots in Python, such as using the sqrt function from the math library.

What will we get as an output? For example, when starting the program, the coefficients a , b , c are requested. Let's enter 1, 4, 4, respectively. As a result, the program will give the following result: Discriminant $D = 0.00$; $x = -2.00$.

Another example. Let's introduce the coefficients: 2, 6, 7. As a result, we get the Discriminant $D = -20.00$; There are no roots.

It should be noted that this program code calculates the roots of the quadratic equation only for the case when the coefficient a is not equal to 0[7].

CONCLUSIONS

Programming is a very exciting hobby. It is unlikely that it can leave anyone indifferent. Computer literacy skills help anyone solve everyday and professional tasks. Programming develops computational thinking. This is a set of methods for solving problems in the field of computer science, applicable in any field. For example, informatics helps in education[8].

In the course of the study, the history of the creation of the Python programming language was studied. The main advantages and disadvantages of the Python programming language were also analyzed. When writing the work, the solution of quadratic equations was studied. Further, using the available information, I wrote a program code for solving quadratic equations. Thus, the goal of the work was achieved, since all the tasks set before the start of the study were solved [9].

It should also be noted that the work has a high practical significance, because, using it, you can check the solved equation, for example, in a lesson in mathematics, physics, and other subjects. And the research hypothesis is confirmed: using the Python programming language, you can solve various mathematical problems, in particular, quadratic equations[10].

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